

Closing the loop in lime-based renders: circular design, material properties and cradle-to-cradle LCA

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Abstract. The massive extraction of virgin raw materials has intensified the focus on the circular economy of building materials. As a Cradle-to-Cradle approach for lime-based construction materials (LBCM) is lacking, this study evaluates the environmental impact and feasibility of creating a fully recycled second-life render (SL) through a closed-loop upcycling process for first-life renders (FL). A second-life binder was thermally activated (900, 1000, 1100, 1200 °C), and its microstructure, compressive strength, and thermal conductivity were investigated. SL had up to 33% open porosity (FL 29%), compressive strength ranged from 2.5 to 3.4 MPa (FL 4.4 MPa), and thermal conductivity from 1.002 to 1.107 W/mK (FL 1.231 W/mK). SL and FL resistance against sulfate attack was equivalent, per RILEM TC 271-ASC recommendation. Environmental impact indicators confirm that the second-life render can reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 55%. This research highlights sustainability gains through circular practices in the life cycle of LBCM.

Research purpose, methodology and main findings

This research assess the feasibility of producing a fully recycled, second-life lime render through a closed-loop upcycling process, eliminating the need for virgin hydrated lime and aggregate. In the study, the technical material properties and environmental key performance indicators of these recycled lime renders are compared, with first-life lime renders made solely from virgin raw materials. By quantifying the benefits of a closed-loop circular economy, this research contributes to understanding the environmental advantages over the traditional linear (cradle-to-grave) economy scenario. Figure 1 details the research methodology. The key findings are described below:

- The fines from the mechanical separation of a first life render used as raw material for the second life binder exhibited a composition of 50% CaCO₃, 44% SiO₂ and 6% Ca(OH)₂. Thermal activation at 900 to 1200 °C resulted in the formation of CaO, consumption of SiO₂ and the formation of clinker phases.
- Microstructure characterization revealed higher porosity in second-life renders compared to the first-life render, attributed to the dilution of the second-life binder by inert SiO₂. Porosity decreased with an increase in calcination temperature. X-ray

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micro-CT analysis confirmed the higher porosity of recycled renders. FL and SL renders show a unimodal pore size distribution with predominantly small pores below $1E+07 \mu\text{m}^3$.

Fig. 1. Research methodology to assess materials' properties, service life (a, b) and sustainability performance (c) of upcycled second-life versus first-life renders

- Second-life renders exhibited 20 to 40% lower compressive strength (compared to the reference), with the best performance observed for calcination of the recycled binder at 1200°C. Conversely, thermal conductivity increased with reduced porosity and higher calcination temperature. The SL-1000 sample was identified as the treatment that balances the effects of processing temperature and technical properties.
- Debris collected after accelerated weathering was slightly higher for FL than for SL, attributed to lower space availability within their pore microstructure. This agreed with open porosity, micro-CT, water absorption coefficient and ultrasonic pulse velocity tests.
- The environmental assessment showed that from Cradle-to-Gate 25% CO₂ emissions can be cut for the SL-1000 compared to FL. The Cradle-to-Cradle scenario is more eco-efficient than the Cradle-to-Grave, leading to reductions ranging from 17 to 55% emissions when relevant material properties.

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